

Producing and Managing FAIR research data in the Humanities

An attempt using Geovistory Toolbox and OntoME

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Introduction. Geovistory is a virtual research and data management environment for the humanities & social sciences. It supports the entire workflow of historical knowledge production: From the creation and management of academically validated statements about the past interlinked with textual and tabular sources, and the (spatial) analysis of research data, to the publication of research data in graphical interfaces and as rdf-triples. Coupled with OntoME it produces reusable research data and allows publishing results and data in accordance with the FAIR principles.

With the shift from a primarily analogue-based to a primarily digital-based working context in Humanities research, data modelling should by now have gained the interest of growing numbers of Humanities scholars. After all, in-depth analysis of digital research data is only feasible when the data are properly modelled. Furthermore, knowledge

of shared ontologies and vocabularies is indispensable when it comes to making data ready for reuse by humans and machines alike—an important prerequisite for replication studies and for compliance to the FAIR data principles. Thus far, however, scholars from all but a few sub-disciplines of the Humanities have largely ignored the subject of formal data modelling.¹

This is set to become a pressing issue; ongoing digitization processes are about to multiply the amount of digital data that researchers in the Humanities have at their disposal. Data, moreover, that often contain vague, fragmentary, uncertain and contradictory observations.

While most members of the Digital Humanities community will be aware of the importance of proper data modelling and compliance with the FAIR principles, we observe that practice lags behind ideals. There is no reason why it should be like this: the task of aligning complex Humanities data with shared ontologies and vocabularies is not as tedious and difficult as scholars might think and brings multiple benefits. Concrete tools, such as Geovistory [2021] and OntoME [2021] are available to support researchers in this process.

Geovistory is an innovative digital tool that allows researchers and heritage professionals to manage their data and make it accessible to both the research community and the wider public. To this end, Geovistory digitally supports the entire workflow of historical knowledge production: From the collection of sources, to the creation and management of academically validated statements about the past or metadata (as research data) interlinked with textual and tabular sources, management of project-specific vocabularies, the creation of information networks and the (spatial) analysis of research data, to the publication of research data in graphical interfaces and as rdf-triples. Geovistory allows managing research data beyond a single project as one can continue building on the created research data or share it with colleagues without creating duplicates due to the innovative project-perspective of a unique information-graph of statements about the past shared among all projects in Geovistory.

In order to produce open and reusable data according to the FAIR principles, each statement in Geovistory is given a unique identifier (findable), modelled according to the CIDOC-CRM standard (ISO 21127:2014) and domain specific extensions (interoperable), produced under creative commons BY-SA 4.0 license (reusable) and will be published in machine and human readable interfaces (accessible). This digital research process is integrated with the “Ontology Management

¹ Gonzalez-Perez 2012.

Environment” OntoME, which is operated by the “Laboratoire de recherche historique Rhône-Alpes” (Lyon) within the Data for History Consortium. A poster of this workflow was presented at the annual Time Machine conference 2019 [Beretta et al. 2019].

This workshop will share a concrete experience of how this workflow has been applied to textual source material and various sets of structured data. It will shed light how a rather generic digital tool is geared towards managing a specific set of research data using a high-level ontology and extensions, how this data can be managed, curated, visualized and be used for further research. The workshop will end with a discussion with the participants on the benefits, but also challenges of working with such tools.

The workshop will present this workflow in three parts building on each other, followed by a Q&A session with the public:

- **Part 1:** Mapping the input data to existing ontologies using OntoME
 - *A collaborative Ontology Management system translating research questions into workflows of semantic data production.*
- **Part 2:** Importing the ontology & data into the data management platform Geovistory
 - *A virtual research environment provides services for FAIRification of historical research data.*
- **Part 3:** Visualizing and publishing the created knowledge graph
 - *Accessing and retrieving the data for further usage.*
- **Discussion**

Bibliographie

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